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CHATBOT ASSISTANT SYSTEM

Abstract- The project entitled as “**Chatbot assistant system**” A chatbot is a computer programme that allows people to communicate with it using natural language and artificial intelligence methods like NLP (natural language processing), which makes the chatbot more dependable and interactive. Chatbot system is popular, therefore many websites are using it. One doesn't even need to search for online purchasing with the chatbot—they may immediately speak to the customer service line. A chatbot can be used to order food, propose products, provide customer service, check the weather, help with personal finances, organise meetings, find and monitor flights, send money, and many other things. A bot is trained on, and when answering queries, it does so in accordance with the training and some pre-established rules. The term for it is "ruled-based approach." Making these bots is rather simple when using this ruled-based method. However, it is insufficient for the bot to respond to queries whose pattern does not line up with the set of training criteria. These bots can be made using the Artificial Intelligence Markup Language (AIML) programming language. It is an XML-based language that enables the developer to specify the guidelines that the bot should abide by.

Keywords – Chatbot, Machine learning, Natural language processor, Artificial Intelligence, Answer Bot.

Introduction- A chatbot is a computer programme that can mimic a discussion or chat with a user in natural language using messaging applications, websites, or mobile applications. It should be accessible around-the-clock and capable of interacting with people in accordance with their input. As the use of smart devices and IoT technology increased, chatbots were created and quickly gained popularity. A chatbot is one of the most innovative and promising methods for interacting with machines. Popular chatbots include

those from Facebook, Slack, Google Assistant, Amazon Alexa, and many more. These are incredibly useful, but in the age of ever-improving technology, as technology is upgraded daily, consumer expectations also rise. The chatbot's user wants it to be more automated. Chatbots are developed using AIML and LSA. Chatbots are created using Artificial Intelligence Markup Language (AIML) and Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA), and they are used to design broad pattern-based questions. The chatbot can utilise this pattern to generate random answers to the same question. Python's Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) technology is used to identify similarities between words as vector representations. so that LSA will interpret AIML's unanswered questions as a response.

Types of chatbot

- 1. Rule-based chatbots** use prewritten scripts to provide users with straightforward responses to their questions. Every response is predetermined and kept in a library. An end user must select a question from a list or formulate their own question in accordance with established guidelines in order to communicate with these chatbots. The laws of conversation include essential sentences that invite related responses. Using scripted chatbots, you may perform activities like gathering contact information or offering simple customer care.
- 2. Self-learning bots** are built using cutting-edge natural language processing (NLP) methods. These methods are combined with basic neural networks to simulate human behaviour. For example, neural networks can learn from questions posed during conversations and provide responses. Due to their capacity to comprehend subtleties in speech, chatbots powered by AI are more effective, adaptable, and well-liked. Smart chatbots, in particular, have the ability to assess user intent, manage complex queries, and offer tailored responses.

How chatbot works

Chatbot uses AI and ML to understand human words, or a human conversation, and use pre build solution flows that help to give a solution.

In the past, chatbots were text-based and trained to respond to a small number of straightforward questions with previously written responses. When faced with a complex topic or one that the developers hadn't anticipated, they failed. They functioned like an interactive FAQ and, while they performed admirably for the particular queries and

answers on which they had been trained. More rules and natural language processing have been incorporated into chatbots over time so that end users can interact with them in a conversational style. In fact, modern chatbots may learn as they encounter more and more human language since they are contextually aware. Natural language understanding (NLU) is a technique used by modern AI chatbots to ascertain the user's needs. AI communication bots must first be properly trained and outfitted with programmed responses. However, because they draw on prior interactions, they don't require manual updating in the future. AI bots are able to read customer moods and comprehend numerous languages. They can now tailor their conversation with the user as a result.

Design

The process of establishing the architecture, parts, modules, interfaces, and data for a specific system in order to meet predetermined requirements is known as systems design. The application of different systems theory to product development could be called systems design. The fields of systems analysis, systems architecture, and system designing have some overlap. A chatbot is a computer programme that uses patterns to mimic a conversation with human users, particularly online. They are our virtual assistants who provide a variety of services via online chat. You need an AIML package (Artificial Intelligence Markup Language) to create artificial intelligence chatbots in Python. Now, check for some files that are already available to code your own AIML files. Take a look at the files on the Alice Bot website, for instance. The startup file we'll be making will function

independently. We will therefore have more AIML files without changing the source code as a result. As soon as there are enough AIML files to load, the programme will begin to operate. This served as an introduction to creating Python-based AI chatbots. Let's go on and examine which specific library can be used to create an AI chatbot.

Data flow diagram

Testing and Implementation

The success of a chatbot deployment depends on testing. Before introducing the chatbot into the production environment, businesses must carry out thorough testing to find and address any problems. Functional, performance, and security testing should all be conducted. The chatbot can be deployed to the production environment when it has been evaluated and authorised. Usability testing is one form of test that entails watching

consumers interact with the chatbot and obtaining feedback on their experience. This kind of testing can assist in identifying areas where the chatbot may be unclear or challenging to use, as well as areas where users may be irritated or having trouble attaining their objectives. A/B testing is a new kind of experiment that compares the performance of two or more iterations of the chatbot with various user groups. This kind of testing can be helpful in figuring out the best ways to arrange conversation flows, as well as other crucial design components. When putting a chatbot into use, selecting a chatbot platform is crucial. The platform should be compatible with the demands of the business, the capabilities of the chatbot, and any necessary message channels. now are numerous chatbot platforms out now, from straightforward drag-and-drop applications to more complex programming frameworks. The degree of flexibility and control you require, the scope and difficulty of your chatbot project, and the availability of messaging channel connectors should all be taken into account when selecting a chatbot platform.

Conclusion

In this project, we have introduced a chatbot that is able to interact with users. This chatbot can answer queries in the textual user input.

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